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ELECTRONIC BANKING SERVICE QUALITY PARAMETERS' IMPACT ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION. (A STUDY CONDUCTED IN WOLAITA SODO , ETHIOPIA)

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ABSTRACT

Objective of the research is to measure the service quality in electronic banking, to improve the customer's satisfaction and to examine the different dimensions of service quality to relate them with expectation of customers. The Importance of the subject of electronic banking service and the importance of focusing on the service provided by the banks adopted, this study use seven dimensions that are very important to provide this service and they are: Reliability, Ease to use, privacy and security, Accessibility, Efficiency, Responsiveness and Cycle time, where the aim of this study is to measure the impact electronic banking on customer satisfaction.

The study sample consisted of 460 customers from who use electronic banking: through simple regression, the results indicated that there is an effect of electronic banking services to reach customer satisfaction. The results showed that there is a statically significant impact of the overall service quality dimensions of electronic banking customer satisfaction. In this research the gap between perception and expectation of e-banking is analyzed by using paired t-test and it shows statically significant gap between perception and expectation of e-banking.

Keywords: Internet Banking, Customer perception, Service quality, Customer Satisfaction

INTRODUCTION

Electronic banking is an innovation that has progressively rendered itself in pervasive ways cutting across several financial institutions and other sectors of the economy. During the 21st century mobile banking advanced from providing mere text messaging services to that of pseudo internet banking where customers could not only view their balances and set

up multiple types of alerts but also transact activities such as fund transfers, deposit cheques via the mobile phone and instruct payroll based transactions (Vaidya 2011).

Daniel (1999) defines electronic banking as the delivery of banks' information and services by banks to customers via different delivery platforms that can be used with different terminal devices such as a personal computer and a mobile phone with browser or desktop software, telephone or digital television.

According to Khan (2007), Internet (electronic) banking includes the system that enables financial institution customers, individuals or businesses, access accounts, transact business, or obtain information on financial products and services on public or private network including Internet,

According to Saha and Zhao (2005), in many ways, E-banking is like traditional payment, inquiry, and information processing systems, differing only in that it utilizes a different delivery channel. Any decision to adopt E-banking is normally influenced by a number of factors. These include customer service enhancement and competitive costs, all of which motivate banks to assess their service.

Many researchers appreciate that electronic banking (e-banking) is defined to include the provision of retail and small value banking products and services through electronic channels as well as large value electronic payments and other wholesale banking services delivered electronically(Georgescu, 2005).

Technology has greatly advanced playing a major role in improving the standards of service quality. Days are long gone when customers would queue in the banking halls waiting to pay their utility bills, school fees or any other financial transactions. They can now do this at their convenience by using e-banking from the comfort of their homes. Additionally due to the tremendous growth of the mobile phone industry mobile phone network providers to offer services to their clients.

E-banking became possible in early 1990s when the Internet was opened to commercial use. With the 24\7 availability of Internet commerce websites, it has become very important to the users to trace and track their transactions, as they occur to ensure the account status and stability. Thus, it has become very important to have banks that can serve, support and work with e-commerce companies and consumers 24\7.

Many electronic banking delivery channels provide banking service to customers. Among them ATM, POS, Mobile banking and internet banking are the most widely used.

ETHIOPIAN ELECTRONIC BANKING SERVICE

Commercial Bank of Ethiopia (CBE), introduced ATM service for local users in 2001 with its fleet of eight ATMs located in Addis Ababa. Moreover, CBE has had Visa membership since November 14, 2005. However, due to lack of appropriate infrastructure it failed to reap the fruit of its membership. Despite, being the pioneer in introducing ATM based payment system and acquired Visa membership, CBE lagged behind private banks, which worked aggressively to maintain its lead in electronic payment systems. The Ethiopian banking industry entering in to this ICT based service to customer in order to bring efficiency in operation by minimizing operating cost thereby increasing customer satisfaction and profitability. E-banking offers the convenience of conducting most of the banking transactions at a time that suits the customer. The customer can access funds and transfer funds between accounts, Pay bills and make purchases 24 hours a day, 7 days a week.

Though there are few researches done about electronic banking in Ethiopia electronic banking is a useful topic to study how to make it applicable using the available Information Communication Technology infrastructures together with the existing financial and legal frameworks so that the quality of services in Ethiopian banking sector can be enhanced for the future. Moreover Internet banking has been widely studied in developed countries and also to some extent in developing countries but not in Ethiopia. Very few studies have been done in developing countries, and it has not been well investigated in Ethiopia. Customers in Ethiopia are late adopters of the Internet and its applications with regards to electronic banking. It looks that electronic banking is facing difficulties in Ethiopia. Ethiopian banking system is still underdeveloped compared to the rest of the world and electronic payment systems are at an embryonic stage. Among commercial banks in Ethiopia very few of them are engaged with the diffusion of e-commerce. Moreover among several services of e-banking, they are limited to ATM service.

CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

Customer satisfaction is it refers to the extent to which customers are happy with the products and/or services provided by a business. Further definition of customer satisfaction is it is a term generally used to measure a customer's perception of a company's products and/or services. It's not a straight forward science however, as customer satisfaction will vary from

person to person, depending on a whole host of variables which may be both psychological and physical. The usual measures of customer satisfaction involve a survey with a set of statements using a Likert Technique or scale (Westbrook, 1980).

Customer satisfaction is the important factor for the long term success of the organization. By keeping the importance of customer satisfaction in mind there is a need of banks to maintain close and stable relationship with their customers by providing the high quality of product and services. So there is a need to judge the level of customer satisfaction. The satisfaction of customer cannot be measured unless the factors which affect the satisfaction level of customers are not determined. As the banking industry is the high involvement industry. Banks are being aware of the importance of this fact that the provision of high quality service to customers is necessary for their survival and the success in today's global and competitive environment (Wang, Han, & Wen, 2003).

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Satisfying customers is the first major mission and purpose of any business organization. It is when customers are satisfied the organizations achieves higher sales, profit and market share and vice versa.

E banking is adopted by banks so as to improve their service delivery, minimize waiting time in the banking hall, enable customers withdraw cash 24/7, aid payment and remittance, request for online statement, or even transfer deposit to a third party account. the benefits banks derive from Electronic Banking in banking operations especially with respect to service delivery is improved efficiency and effectiveness of their operations so that more transactions can be processed faster and most conveniently, which will undoubtedly impact significantly on the overall performance of the banks. Currently there are some factors which affect customer satisfaction in electronic banking service in commercial bank of Ethiopia. Those are:

1. ATM machines are out of cash, no printing statements, cards get blocked, frequent breakdown of ATM service, unreliability of ATM service, lack of sufficient technicians in all bank who solve breakdown of ATM machine, lack of sufficient alternative system which substitute ATM service
2. Lack of convenience of E-bank service, lack of credit card service, under-development of technological infrastructure, low level of relevant knowledge creation and innovation, interruption of network, lack of suitable and regulatory frame work for e-commerce,

3. Resistance to changes in technology among customers and service providers as result of fear of risk,
4. Lack of fair distribution of E-banking service in all over Ethiopia during this pretest of this study
5. Long Queues are still seen at the banking hall, bank customers still handle too much cash, and hardly do people talk about the electronic banking products that are available commercial bank of Ethiopia branches

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- To assess customers expectation of service quality parameters of electronic banking.
- To asses customers perception of service quality parameters of electronic banking.
- To assess the service quality gap of electronic banking and identifying the relative significance of gap parameters
- To find out the electronic banking service dimensions that has impact on customer satisfaction.

RESEARCH MODEL

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

Based on research model and literature review the following hypotheses are formulated for study

H1. There is a significant relationship between reliability and customer satisfaction toward electronic banking

H2: There is a significant relationship between security and customer satisfaction toward electronic banking

H3: There is a significant relationship between responsiveness and customer satisfaction toward electronic banking

H4: There is significant relationship between efficiency and customer satisfaction toward electronic Banking

H5: There is a significant relationship between ease of use and customer satisfaction toward Electronic banking

H6: There is significant difference between branch visits after e-banking and before e-banking

H7: There is significant relationship between accessibility and customer satisfaction toward electronic Banking

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study has been conducted based on primary data collected through structured questionnaires. Since the approach aims at finding out the level of emotional intelligence of Indian teachers working in Wolaita Sodo University, the research design has been taken to be Descriptive. The measurement scale for the instrument is considered five point Likert Scale representing the intervals. The survey is Census (61) against the limited number of Indian Teachers in the University.

The primary data has been collected through structured questionnaires consisting of Questions regarding accessibility, Responsiveness, Privacy & Security, responsiveness, Reliability, cycle time ,efficiency. The research design is a casual research so as to obtain detailed information that helps the researcher to establish the relationship between electronic banking and customer satisfaction at commercial bank of Ethiopia Wolita Sodo. The measurement scale for the instrument is considered five point Likert Scale representing the intervals. The survey is based on stratified random sampling and data is collected collect the data from the sample size of 460 bank customers. The study population comprised of electronic banking customers of commercial bank of Ethiopia 4 branches Wolita Sodo, Dicha ,Tona and Wadu.

ANALYSIS & DISCUSSION

Table 1: The service quality parameters gap between expectation and perception

p		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	df	Sig (2-tailed)
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	Perception on reliability – expectation on reliability	.22465	.96616	.04505	.13613	.31318	4.987	459	.000
Pair 2	perception on ease to use – expectation on ease to use	-.20972	.81115	.03782	-.28404	-.13540	-5.545	459	.000
Pair 3	Perception on Accessibility - Expectation on Accessibility	-.34375	.87201	.04066	-.42365	-.26385	-8.455	459	.000
Pair 4	Perception on security and privacy - Expectation on security and privacy	-.21458	.84567	.03943	-.29207	-.13710	-5.442	459	.000
Pair 5	Perception on Efficiency - Expectation on Efficiency	-.50327	.80091	.03738	-.57673	-.42980	-13.462	458	.000
Pair 6	Perception on Responsiveness - Expectation on Responsiveness	-.22600	.77065	.03593	-.29661	-.15539	-6.290	459	.000
Pair 7	Perception on cycle time – expectation on cycle time	-.22594	.90816	.04234	-.30915	-.14273	-5.336	459	.000

According to table 1 all the service quality gap difference is significant that on the case of reliability perception is greater than Expectation so in this case customers are satisfied with Reliability of electronic banking but in all other case perception is less than Expectation that mean customers need is not met. When researcher sees the gap between perception and expectation of seven service quality gap parameters, the difference is high in the case of efficiency and very low in the case of ease to use parameter. In the case of efficiency the gap between perception and expectation is .50327 which is highest gap when

researcher compares the gap with other gap. The gap is very low in case of ease to use parameter in -ve sign which indicate that, even the gap is low, customer are not satisfied because perception is much lower than that of expectation. The only positive difference is that of reliability gap which is .22465 in the case customers are satisfied in reliability parameter of electronic banking. Standard deviation is high in case of reliability which is about .96616 where as low in case of responsiveness which is .77065. The Sig. (2-tailed) is .000 in all case which indicates the difference or the gap is significant.

Table 2 : Summary of all service quality gaps

Paired Differences	Mean	Mean Difference	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	df	Sig(2-tailed)
					Lower	Upper			
Perception - Expectation	4.0043	-.16785	.58706	.02737	-.22164	-.11406	-6.132	459	.000
	3.8365								

Over all service quality gap shows significant difference between perception and expectation of electronic banking. the mean difference is .1678 as indicated in above table which is the difference of perception mean 4.0043 and expectation mean of 3.8365.the difference is significant because of that the p – value is less than .05 and it indicates that customers dissatisfaction .

Table 3: Impact of all seven service quality parameters on customer satisfaction by multiple Regression

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
.901a	.811	.809	.264

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	135.680	7	19.383	277.879	.000b
Residual	31.528	452	.070		
Total	167.209	459			

a Dependent Variable: customer satisfaction

b Predictors: (Constant), Perception on cycle time, Perception on reliability, Perception on Responsiveness, Perception on security and privacy, Perception on Efficiency, perception on ease to use, Perception on Accessibility

	Un standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	-.141	.100		-1.406	.161
Perception on reliability	.123	.022	.137	5.588	.000
perceptions on ease to use	.184	.030	.203	6.228	.000
Perception on Accessibility	.258	.032	.288	7.970	.000
Perception on security and privacy	.045	.028	.048	1.619	.106
Perception on Efficiency	.149	.027	.168	5.490	.000
Perception on Responsiveness	.139	.026	.152	5.242	.000
Perception on cycle time	.138	.020	.162	6.915	.000

From above table we can infer that all the variables have impacts on customer satisfaction at significant level but Accessibility has more power to explain customer satisfaction when compared with others accessibility can explain up to 25.8% and security and privacy got less share which is only 4.5 And at the insignificant level as indicated by p value which indicate that peoples are less interested in security and privacy issue when they see it with others but in single way it gives value to customers . The results generated by the seven factors explain 81 percent of the variation. That mean from overall satisfaction 81% explained by these variables.

Analysis of p- values states that reliability, ease of use, accessibility, efficiency, responsiveness & cycle time have significant impact on customer satisfaction as the p value is less than .005 (it is .000) while in case of security & privacy p value is more than .005 (it is .106) means security & privacy has no significant impact on customer satisfaction. Hence H1, H3, H4,H5, H6, H7 are accepted and H2 is rejected.

CONCLUSION

The study result shows that there are positive or statistically significance impact service quality dimensions of e-banking on customer satisfaction .Based on the result of regression analysis the researcher conclude that there is statistically significant relationship

between reliability and customer satisfaction ,ease to use and customer satisfaction, efficiency and customer satisfaction accessibility and customer satisfaction ,responsiveness and customer satisfaction , cycle time and customer satisfaction .

In view of the findings of this study it is concluded that electronic banking in Ethiopia creates significant impact on service delivery. Based on the result researcher conclude that there is significant gap between expectation and perception of customers on service quality measurement of e-banking service such as reliability , ease to use ,efficiency , accessibility and cycle time and security and privacy.

In view of the finding of this study it is concluded that expectation of customers about electronic banking service is higher than that of perception at significant level this leads to dissatisfaction of services of electronic banking by customers

From result of paired T- test all the service quality determinants tasted in paired t-test states that except reliability are below expectation of customers at significant level. Whereas, in case of efficiency difference between expectation and perception is high that shows that the E-banking efficiency is far below the expectation of customers that mean it is not easy to find the service of electronic banking. In case of Ease to use the gap between expectation and perception is small when compared with others. Generally the gap between expectation and perception shows there is significant difference.

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